

India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC): Potential and Challenges for India and Middle-East

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Abstract: This paper analyses the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) and underlines different perspectives and strategic dimensions. The role of IMEC in economic, political, strategic and energy security. It leads to the integration of economies, regional security and prosperity. This pact focuses on togetherness, having the same geostrategic goals, and countering China's Belt Road Initiative (BRI). It emphasised maritime security, India as an integral part of the world, and that it also acts as a transit route for Southeast Asian countries. It enhances regional connectivity, transportation infrastructure, and logistical efficiencies, crucial milestones in shifting global order. It develops diplomatic collaboration, secures regional supply chains, and promotes sustainable development. IMEC also promotes cultural ties and people-to-people interactions, fostering mutual understanding across diverse regions. As IMEC promotes infrastructure development, it may spur innovation in logistics, digital connectivity, and innovative technologies that redefine how goods and services flow globally.

Keywords: Integration, Connectivity, Collaboration, Security, Innovation, Sustainability.

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Introduction

The Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed at the G20 summit in 2023 in New Delhi to establish the 'India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor' (IMEC); the signing partners were India, the US, Saudi Arabia, the European Union, UAE, France, Germany, and Italy. The envisioned corridor aims to cut transit times between its eastern and western endpoints by 40% and reduce transportation costs by 30% (although some experts call it Debatable) compared to the traditional Suez Canal route. The IMEC will incorporate a combination of railways, ship-to-rail networks (including road and sea transport), and road routes with two primary corridors:

The Eastern Corridor will connect India's western section to the Arabian Gulf, promoting enhanced regional connectivity and facilitating trade. In addition to Dammam and Ras Al Khair ports in Saudi Arabia, it connects important regional Indian ports, including Mundra, Kandla, and the Jawaharlal Nehru Port Trust, with ports in the United Arab Emirates, such as Fujairah, Jebel Ali, and Abu Dhabi. Additionally, a railway line will link the ports of Fujairah (UAE) and Haifa (Israel), travelling via Saudi Arabian cities such as Ghuwaifat and Haradh before continuing into Jordan.

This network increases economic and geopolitical cooperation and strengthens trade relations.

The Northern Corridor connects the Arabian Peninsula (Saudi Arabia and the UAE) to Europe (France, Italy and The United States), linking key ports such as Haifa in Israel. In Europe, it connects Piraeus in Greece, Messina in southern Italy, and Marseille in France.

The goal is to establish a dependable and cost-efficient cross-border ship-to-rail transit network, facilitating the movement of goods and services to, from, and within India, the UAE, Saudi Arabia, Jordan, Israel, and Europe. Participants also intend to enable cables for electricity and digital connectivity (high-speed data cables) along the railway route and a pipe for clean hydrogen export. The Partnership for Global Infrastructure and Investment (PGII) includes the initiative. PGII is viewed as a challenge to China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) and was unveiled in 2021 during the G-7 summit in the UK. PGII is a transparent, high-impact, values-driven infrastructure partnership that aids countries with low to middle incomes and massive infrastructure needs.

The IMEC objects to increasing efficiency, reducing costs, stable regional supply chains, enhancing trade accessibility and economic

cooperation, generating jobs, and lowering greenhouse gas emissions. The IMEC has enormous potential to transform the connected countries economically, politically and geographically with future possibilities to evaluate whether the IMEC can lay the ground for global integration and trade assistance even though the corridor has specific regional threats from China, Pakistan and Iran with some global nexus between Russia and India, Rising Saudi and Chinese integration, Iran and Israel confrontation and Issues from Greece and Türkiye.

Picture from FRONTLINE (Oct 05, 2023)

Geostragic Potential and Challenges

Recently, during his speech at the United Nations in September 2024, Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu of Israel presented the world with two contrasting perspectives on security and threats: the 'Map of THE BLESSING' and the 'Map of THE CURSE.' The Map of THE BLESSING emphasises the vast potential for growth, development, peace, and security, while the Map of THE CURSE highlights threats to peace and economic stagnation.

The map of THE BLESSING shows the same countries that are part of the India-Middle East-European Economic Corridor (IMEC), with Israel as the primary beneficiary of the corridor. It has the potential to give alternate routes to the Strait of Bab el Mandeb and the Red Sea, which are vulnerable to proxies of Iran, like the Houthis and al-Tarik in Yemen and Somalia's al-Shabaab and Ansar al-sharia. This is also an alternative to the Suez Canal, significantly impacted by climate change and Egypt's monopoly.

This pact holds significant potential in maintaining regional stability and fostering long-lasting peace between Arabs and Israel. It could pave the way for Israel and Palestine settlement and conflict resolution, a longstanding point of contention between the Arab world and Israel. The framework shows how dedicated the US, Europe, and new countries like Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and India are to forge a more linked and equitable Eurasian order. Recently, Italy withdrew from the Belt Road Initiative (BRI), further underscoring the importance of the corridor. The India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) is not a direct alternative to China's BRI but is part of the global response to

counter China's growing economic influence. Unlike the BRI, which has focused mainly on infrastructure financing in developing countries, the IMEC prioritises establishing a network of high-efficiency trade routes through cutting-edge technology, green energy solutions, and digital infrastructure. IMEC's emphasis on sustainable energy solutions and connectivity makes it an attractive option for countries seeking alternatives to avoid the debt traps associated with BRI projects.

From a geopolitical perspective, the continuous conflict between Israel and Gaza, with Jordan's limited involvement and Saudi Arabia's harsh criticism, makes it difficult for Israel, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates to cooperate as envisioned in the IMEC actively. Additionally, the corridor raises geoeconomic concerns for countries like Egypt and Turkey, which feel excluded. Egypt sees the proposed corridor as threatening its lucrative control over the Suez Canal. However, Turkey maintains its strategic position as a bridge connecting Asia and Europe by arguing that a rail link through Basra and Iraq would be more practical.

Benjamin Netanyahu has included India in the map of THE BLESSINGS, which signifies its importance. India is the transit point that connects the Middle East and Europe to South East Asian countries. India has to balance rising engagement with Africa, particularly the Horn of Africa, countries around the Gulf of Aden and Bab-el Mandeb. Trade and oil imports from Iran account for 24% in December 2024, according to Indian Express; the recent 10-year contract with Iran on Chabahar port brings safety concerns between the United States and India.

While the India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) holds great promise, its implementation is not guaranteed. The corridor is expected to run through geopolitically sensitive areas such as the Middle East, where conflicts, political instability, and regional rivalries could pose significant risks. For instance, the war in Gaza has delayed the project's progress. Infrastructure bottlenecks, such as the need for substantial upgrades to rail and port facilities in some participating countries, may also delay the expected efficiency gains (East Asia Forum, 2024). For the IMEC to succeed, participating countries must align on an actionable implementation plan that addresses these challenges head-on. Only by doing so can the IMEC realise its potential to drive global trade, secure energy transitions, and offer a robust alternative to existing trade routes.

Economics of IMEC: Potential and Challenges

The India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) aims to connect a combined GDP of US\$47 trillion with a comprehensive infrastructure network, focusing on high-efficiency trade routes, renewable energy, digital infrastructure, and improved international communication networks. The Suez Canal and the Red Sea are vital maritime routes, handling around 30% of the world's container traffic and over \$1 trillion in annual merchandise (World Economic Forum, 2024). However, security problems exist because these routes are open to armed organisations. With 'high-speed goods trains running at 120 kmph—about four times quicker than ships', IMEC provides a 'possible alternative route that might drastically reduce transit times, enabling a trade with Europe 40% faster than the Suez Canal maritime route' (ISAS, 2024). While the Red Sea's significance has declined, contributing just 11% of global trade flows according to the World Economic Forum (WEF), IMEC may offer some relief but is unlikely to replace the Suez Canal entirely. The Suez Canal remains crucial to

international trade due to its established infrastructure and centrality in global maritime logistics.

This initiative holds great potential to bolster global trade efficiency and ensure energy security. The India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) is more than just a trade route for products and services. A secure high-speed data pipeline is also planned in light of the escalating cybersecurity concerns, which may pave the door for India to export its software and IT services to Europe and West Asia. By linking the two hemispheres of Asia and Europe, the IMEC's agreement on standards offers a roadmap for accelerating economic growth among the participating economies. Given that the member economies generate USD 47 trillion, or roughly half of the world's GDP, as per the Financial Express, the IMEC's strength as an economic force is unquestionable.

This corridor is even more critical since India's exports go via the Red Sea, Suez Canal, and Bab-el Mandab to Europe and the US, its two biggest export markets. As improved infrastructure lowers shipping costs and production-linked incentives (PLI) programs boost manufacturing, India's integration into global value chains is expected to increase. India's most significant commercial partner is the European Union (EU), with bilateral trade reaching an anticipated US\$136 billion in 2022–2023. India's exports surpass US\$61 billion, making it its second-largest export market. With US\$78.5 billion in exports in 2022–2023, the US is India's top export destination but its second-largest trading partner. Promoting the IMEC as a backup corridor that offers some redundancy to the current trade route would be strategically advantageous for India as its trade with the US and Europe expands.

Piyush Goyal, then Minister of Commerce and Industry, emphasised the potential for increased cooperation between Mediterranean nations and India, particularly in tourism. He highlighted India's growing market for Mediterranean goods and services, attributing this to the strong historical ties between the two regions. Goyal stressed India as a fast-growing economy globally, valuing 3.5% of Global trade, driven by a high Demographic Dividend, with predictions that India should become the third-largest economy by 2030. Further, Mr Goyal noted that India's efforts like Make in India, Financial Inclusion and Ease of Doing Business aimed to simplify business processes, attract investment and foster economic growth. Sectors like Green energy, production processes, maritime productivity, financial inclusion, pharmaceuticals, services and software technology, sustainable agriculture, and tourism present significant opportunities for investment and collaboration (pib.gov.in, 06 SEP 2024).

According to the External Affairs Ministry, India's bilateral trade with the Levant region is around US dollar 80 billion, with greater interest in sustainability, development technology, defence manufacturing, and infrastructure. India and the Levant region share significant interests in the shipping sector, spanning areas such as ship manufacturing, purchasing, maritime commerce, and the cruise industry. The Indian government is optimistic about fostering a strong partnership with the Levant Region, aiming for mutual economic prosperity and sustainable growth & development. This collaboration promotes a cleaner, more resilient, secure, inclusive, and prosperous future. By reducing reliance on the Suez Canal, the alliance will benefit the European Union by reducing transportation costs and increasing trade with South and Southeast Asia. Additionally, it will diversify the EU's activities

away from Russia and China and increase its geopolitical influence in the Gulf. Gulf nations stand to gain from improved connectivity and creative projects that will strengthen regional stability and economic connections.

Energy Security

The IMEC project has attracted attention for its ambitious green energy and infrastructure plans, but it must also deal with environmental and socio-political risks. Developing solar grids and hydrogen corridors is a significant step toward renewable energy, but the ecological footprint of constructing this massive infrastructure is a concern. While the corridor aims to promote clean hydrogen trade, questions remain about the feasibility of large-scale green hydrogen production and transportation across long distances. Ensuring this energy source is produced using renewable energy rather than fossil fuels will require continuous technological advancements and investments. The India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) also aims to establish a 20,000-kilometre cable system, the Trans Europe Asia system, to enhance global communication networks. Since 95 per cent of the world's communication flows through undersea cables, this initiative is crucial for securing international data transmission (East Asia Forum, 2024)

The India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) also plays a crucial geopolitical role in boosting European energy security. The memorandum outlines plan for a series of energy links within the corridor, including pipelines for transporting green hydrogen and electricity cables. This energy component is crucial for European countries, especially given the EU's ambitious green transition targets and the decoupling of Russian fossil fuels after Russia invaded Ukraine. The EastMed-Poseidon pipeline, a collaborative effort between the Italian energy business Edison and the Greek corporation DEPA International Projects, is slated to carry natural gas from Israel and Cyprus to Greece and Italy. This pipeline closely corresponds with the Mediterranean portion of IMEC. By integrating this 2,000 km pipeline into IMEC's framework, the project would shift from being an isolated initiative to a key part of a strategic corridor. This integration would strengthen the energy infrastructure of IMEC and its broader geopolitical significance, reinforcing its role as a significant component of Europe's energy diversification strategy (European Council on Foreign Relations, 2024). IMEC states are implementing 5G networks in their telecom industries. For security and data transfer considerations, the IMEC countries should thoroughly analyse the mobile networks in their areas and halt the dominance of Chinese companies such as China Unicom, Zhong Xing Telecommunication Equipment (ZTE), and Huawei. To encourage cooperation, IMEC nations can respond by forming task forces or committees on telecom technologies that create concerns for governments and providers.

The India-Middle East-Europe Economic Corridor (IMEC) can facilitate energy resources like crude oil, particularly from the Middle East, a primary source for India and Southeast Asian countries. India's Ministry of External Affairs says, "Our key interests are in fertilisers, clean energy, hydrology and technology, expensive materials like diamonds, defence systems, and cyber security." As one of the world's largest net importers of oil and gas, India heavily relies on overseas energy supplies for sustained economic growth and development. IMEC will improve

infrastructure and enhance exports, fostering stronger integration into global value chains (GVC) through initiatives like the International Solar Alliance (ISA). India's involvement in significant infrastructure projects, including air, water and rail development emphasising green hydrogen initiatives, will further support its strategic connectivity (Financial Express, 2024).

IMEC can play a pivotal role in addressing the energy challenge. It also allows India to enhance its global green energy transition leadership. Two key priority areas have been identified within the IMEC framework to foster energy cooperation. First, the "renewable energy expansion pathway", which hinges on the development of battery storage, is expected to significantly drive up the costs associated with the energy transition. Second, the "Green Hydrogen Corridor" is designed to facilitate the export of green hydrogen, broadening its market reach beyond domestic borders and contributing to a more sustainable and diversified energy future. These initiatives within IMEC can help drive the global shift toward cleaner energy while positioning India as a leader in the green energy sector.

Political Co-Operation and Development

India's involvement in the IMEC reflects its growing diplomatic prowess. The corridor allows India to strengthen its geopolitical alliances with key countries in the Middle East, Europe, and North America while simultaneously countering China's influence on global trade. Similarly, by focusing on the IMEC's economic and strategic benefits, India can consolidate its role as a significant player in international trade networks. The corridor will also promote India's Digital Public Infrastructure, a framework designed to enhance financial inclusion and streamline digital transactions. By integrating Digital Public Infrastructure into the IMEC, India could set new standards in cross-border digital trade and communication.

With over 9 million Indians residing and working in the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC), trade between India and the GCC has recently increased to USD 160–180 billion annually. This region is essential to India's energy needs, economic requirements like remittances, and industrial partnerships like the Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT) with the United Arab Emirates. To counter Pakistan and assist the local Muslim community, India's broader geopolitical policy includes strengthening its ties with the Middle East. Indian companies now have the chance to work together in these new industries as Gulf States like Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates are changing their economy from dependent on oil to relying on tourism. Another vital component of the Middle East strategy, known as Middle East QUAD, is New Delhi's cooperation with Israel, the United Arab Emirates, and the United States through the I2U2 grouping and the IMEC. S. Jaishankar, India's Minister of External Affairs (MEA), highlighted that the I2U2 grouping, focusing on technology, innovation, and sustainability, will become increasingly active. This collaboration is poised to foster deeper engagement in logistics, clean energy, and the defence sector (Financial Express, 2024).

Like Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates, Greece anticipates using IMEC to expand its position in the twenty-first century. Under the BRI, the majority of a strategically positioned Greek port in the Saronic Gulf—a vital link to Europe—is held by the Chinese state-owned China Ocean Shipping Company (COSCO) (Arab Center for Research and

Policy Studies, 2024). The IMEC will be interpreted differently by each country along its route due to varying geopolitical interests and differing views on multipolarity. The United States will likely see IMEC as a strategic tool to curb China's growing economic influence in the Middle East, aiming to pull the GCC states closer to the West. On the other hand, the UAE and Saudi Arabia are likely to view the corridor as a means to diversify their economic relationships, balancing their ties with Europe and North America alongside those with China and other Eastern and Global South nations. In line with their larger goals for economic diversification away from dependency on hydrocarbons, IMEC presents them with a fresh chance to reaffirm their positions as key hubs of interregional connectivity.

According to the UAE and Saudi Arabia, conventional global powers like the US, China, and Russia are not the sole elements that influence the international order. These "middle powers" see themselves as influential players in the evolving geopolitical landscape. The ripple effects of the Russia-Ukraine conflict, including energy crises in Europe and food shortages across Africa and the Arab world, have given GCC countries like Saudi Arabia the leverage to strengthen their positions as key partners to the Global North and South. While they will continue to support US-led efforts to challenge China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), the UAE and Saudi Arabia will use IMEC as a strategic means to position themselves as essential bridges between East and West, thereby boosting their geopolitical influence in a multipolar world.

IMEC: The Road Ahead

Given the numerous uncertain circumstances in this equation at an early stage and the fact that IMEC was only recently signed, it is challenging to forecast the geostrategic ramifications of this multifaceted corridor. Notwithstanding all of the factors, IMEC is expected to highlight a key distinction between the Gulf Region's and the United States's perspectives on China's ascent and the global shift away from US-led unipolarity. Meanwhile, US officials frequently regard the rivalry between Beijing and Washington as a zero-sum game. Any geo-economic advantages made by China in the region will automatically result in a loss for the West. Some officials in Washington and the capitals of Europe who are hopeful that IMEC will impede China's geo-economics ascent in the Middle East could be misguided. Even though IMEC presents numerous opportunities to enhance Western countries' commercial, trade, energy, investment, and economic ties with the United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia, it is illogical to believe that it will cause the two Gulf Arab countries to turn away from China.

The United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia see their relations with the United States and China as a win-win situation. Saudi Arabian and United Arab Emirates policymakers do not acknowledge that they are faced with the difficult decision of supporting China or the United States in the ongoing economic competition. The GCC members are steadfast in their resolve to concurrently grow their networks in the Global South, the East, and the West. This initiative bears massive advantages to the member states and even regional non-participating countries. The countries experience intensified digital connectivity, economic diversification, and financial growth from the dividends. However, issues like the Israel-Palestine conflicts pose considerable challenges to the corridor's viability and sustainability. Therefore,

addressing the logical, financial, and geopolitical constraints which may delay the project is essential to IMEC's continued prosperity.

India and the IMEC

India has a great future with IMEC as it has excellent relations with Gulf countries such as Saudi Arabia, UAE, Kuwait, and Qatar. Gulf Cooperation countries' trade with India reached above 150 billion Dollars, with the GCC contributing 15% of India's total trade; key growth sectors include energy, defence, and health. IMEC is expected to boost trade between India and Europe by 40%, reducing logistics costs and speeding up trade in goods and services among the member countries. It shifts to Act West policy, I2U2 and India's European Free Trade Association (EFTA). India has Geopolitical and Geo-economic interests in the Middle East due to its linkage to important maritime routes, which boosts anti-terrorist and extremist activities. Middle East region is home to 8 million people of Indian origin, who send remittances of more than \$50 billion a year. India has robust diplomatic ties in the region, including information sharing with Israel, Saudi Arabia, Oman, and the United Arab Emirates and a defence deal with Qatar. India will be able to sustain strong ties with Israel, Iran, and Saudi Arabia, the three poles of power in the Middle East, through diplomatic discussions within countries and regional political stability.

The IMEC offers India a valuable opportunity to better integrate with global value chains (GVCs). Historically, India's protectionist policies have hindered its ability to fully capitalise on the opportunities from shifting GVC dynamics. While initiatives like Production Linked Incentives (PLIs) and the rapid expansion of infrastructure have made strides, these measures have not been enough to attract key global firms and enhance India's position within the global economy. The IMEC, in contrast, counters the protectionist criticisms India faced after its exit from the RCEP by opening avenues for broader collaboration. Giving India and other member states a platform to use their economic complementarities enables Indian MSMEs to join the GVC, increasing the benefits for producers and consumers. Additionally, the IMEC seeks to advance economic growth by enhancing the competitiveness of Indian businesses. It essentially offers a new framework for international connectivity and trade facilitation, but its long-term effectiveness and influence will rely on how it develops and is implemented.

Conclusion

The IMEC presents excellent opportunities and considerable challenges. It could push trade and commerce between the two continents and transform their economic dynamics. The IMEC has obstacles despite its enormous potential since it must foster cooperation among several states with varied goals. The goals of the many IMEC economies, each with unique economic and social traits, must be balanced to accomplish a shared goal, unlike the BRI, which is entirely financed and run by China. For the trade route to be viable and long-lasting, it must also be designed to correspond with market conditions. Meanwhile, events like the October 7 attacks on Israel and its subsequent intervention in Gaza have slowed down the ambitious plans and delayed Arab and Israel resolution. Türkiye being out of the corridor could rise as a potential threat, as recently seen in the Syrian coup d'etat 2024. Experts are of the view to give the project more time to draft and iron out differences for the greater good and cause. However, this

Understanding can transform the agreed countries by unlocking their economic potential. Much of the agreement's success depends on the seriousness and state's needs with the agreement, which ultimately lies in its implementation and strategic importance.

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